

Socio-spatial Analysis of Rural Settlement Types in Darjeeling District

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Abstract: Human Settlement means cluster of dwellings of any type or size where human beings live. For this purpose, people may erect houses and other structures and command some area or territory as their economic support-base. Thus, the process of settlement inherently involves grouping of people and apportioning of territory as their resource base. Settlements vary in size and type. Types of the settlement are determined by the extent of the built-up area and inter-house distance (NCERT). This can be determined by several quantitative techniques and applied methods of rural settlement Geography. As the Himalayas is the tallest, newest and most populated young fold mountain of the world. It always attracts researchers from various fields. Darjeeling is the hilly district of west Bengal (as of 2011 Census). The geographical aspects of the districts attracts the researchers to study over the several components. This paper aims to find out the types of rural settlement in Darjeeling district after Bernhard's method 1931, analyze the social attributes of settlement classification, identification of primary economic function and the concentration of rural settlements in Darjeeling district.

Keywords: Rural settlement, compact, semi-compact, semi-sprinkled, dispersed.

Introduction: The pressure of population in the Indian Himalayas is a matter of concern for researchers at present. Darjeeling is an old colonial city of Eastern Himalaya with a high growth rate of population till now. As the city has become densely populated and the wave of development reached throughout the district, the rural population of the district has also shown a higher growth rate. Rural settlements are an important aspect of settlement and human Geography, because they show the complex relationship of human occupancies of land and the environment. In 2001 the district population was 1,609,172 which has increased to 1,846,823 in 2011. The human settlement of the district has also increased with the rise. Because settlements are seen as a basic manifestation of the relationship between humans and the environment, settlement studies are important in the field of geography (Sharma, 2015). Determining the types of rural settlement is broadly necessary for assessing the overall development of the rural areas of the district and further economic and regional planning of the district or the area under study. There are two factors, physical and cultural, responsible for various settlement types in rural areas. They are also known as agglomerating factors or deglomerating factors. In physical factors relief, fertility of soil, amount of rainfall, dry land and defense are included, while in cultural factors landuse, land tenure, cropping pattern, clan and caste system, social relationships and means of transportation are included. In Darjeeling district, since it is a preferred tourism spot from the British era and rural tourism based on homestay and community participation are at the boom, catering tourist population within local natural and cultural habitat is a concern for recent typology of rural settlement. The study was undertaken in the sub district level to identify the types of rural settlement and conducted through CD Block level data.

Study Area: The selected study area for this recent study is Darjeeling (Darjiling, Census of India 2011) district. The District Darjiling lies in the northernmost part of the State of West Bengal having the shape of an irregular triangle. Geographically, the northern portion of the district is a part of the Great Himalayas which is at the height of 300 to 12000 feet from the mean sea level and in the

southern portion lies in the Tarai region stretching along the base of the hills. Since the data used for this study is based on 2011 Census data, the then Darjeeling district, comprising 12 CD Blocks and Darjeeling, Kalimpong, Kurseong and siliguri, all four subdivisions were taken into account. Administratively, this four Sub-Divisions consisting of 12 Community Development Blocks (C.D. Blocks), namely, (1) Darjeeling-Pulbazar, (2) Rangli Rangliot (3) Kalimpong-I (4) Kalimpong-II (5) Gorubathan (6) Jorebunglow-Sukiapokhri (7) Mirik (8) Kurseong (9) Matigara (10) Naxalbari (11) Phansidewa and (12) Kharibari.

Fig. 1: Decadal Growth of Total and Rural Population of Darjeeling District

Objective: The main objectives of the study are:

- A. To observe and analyze the importance of classification of rural settlement types.
- B. To identify the types of rural settlement and their affecting factors.
- C. Calculate the concentration index using the Bernhard method (1931) for 2011 Census.

Materials and Methods: The present study is mainly based on secondary data from census. Secondary data has mainly been obtained from District Census Handbook, Darjiling, 2011. The technique of the study has been adopted from the formula proposed by Bernhard in 1931. According to that, to conduct the study at sub district level, CD Blocks of Darjeeling district were taken for the spatial analysis. For the reference, some books, census report, research papers and online articles were consulted. To identify the types of rural settlement of the study area and to calculate the degree of concentration for the same, the simple formula of Bernhard (1931) were followed.

$$K = S * M / N$$

Where,

K= Degree of Concentration

S= Area of the CD Blocks

M=Total Number of Houses in the CD Blocks

N= Number of Settlement Groups in the Blocks

Social and Regional Importance of Rural Settlement Classification: Darjeeling district is the only district of West Bengal consisting hills and mountains as a part of the mighty Himalayas. Geographically, hilly areas of Darjeeling are a part of the Shivalik Range or Outer Himalayas. Beyond the mountains in the North, starts the flat plain of the Tarai at South and South-East part of the district. Thus,

the physiography of Darjeeling can be broadly divided into Hills and Plain land (DCHB, Darjiling, 2011). Subsequently the district has temperate climate in the hills and subtropical climate in the Tarai regions. Cultural aspects of settlement development are also different in the two regions. The district is the Tea production and Tourism hub of the state West Bengal as well the eastern India. So, the classification of settlements, grown since the colonial age, and spreading towards the forested villages according to the present day population pressure and demands, needs to be discussed.

- Identification of types of rural settlement helps to study the spatial organization
- Physical and socio-cultural factors affecting rural settlements can be classified.
- Such classification facilitates rural and micro level regional planning.
- Types of settlement often indicate the primary economic function.
- It helps to determine the social structure whether the settlement is caste based, function based or population number based.
- It allows to trace the historical events and preferences of the area forming the present day layout, evolution of rural landscape and population dispersal.
- It supports the theorization of local resource management.

Fig. 2: C.D. Block-wise Number of Villages in Darjeeling District

Result and Discussion: By using the formula stated earlier, it has been resulted that, according to 2011 data, there are four types of rural settlement in Darjeeling district. Table 1 shows the types of rural settlement of each CD Blocks of the district. The Table 2 shows the degree of concentration of the settlements. The identified types of settlement are Compact, Semi-compact, Semi-sprinkle and dispersed.

Table1: Types of Settlements of Darjeeling District, 2011. (After Bernhard 1931)

Sl. No	Name of C.D. Block	Area (S) in Sq. km	No. of Villages	No. of Household (M)	N	Index (K)	Types
1.	Darjeeling-Pulbazar	416	43	22683	1422	6635	C
2.	Rangli-Rangliot	273	29	15304	991	4216	SC
3.	Kalimpong –I	360.46	43	13854	1228	4066	SC
4.	Kalimpong – II	241.26	33	13172	970	3276	SC
5.	Gorubathan	442.72	27	12662	901	6222	C
6.	Jorebunglow-Sukhiapokhri	222.12	42	19489	1440	3006	SC
7.	Mirik	119.18	21	9962	753	1576	SP
8.	Kurseong	372.30	65	17661	2027	3243	SC
9.	Matigara	143	59	28571	1816	2250	SP
10.	Naxalbari	181.88	78	20461	2083	1787	SP
11.	Phansidewa	312.15	103	42138	2950	4459	SC
12.	Kharibari	144.88	73	20737	2400	1251	D

Source: Computed by Researcher

Table 2: Degree of Concentration Index

Sl. No.	Settlement Type	Range of Index	Name of C.D. Blocks	Total No. of Settlements	Total Area (%)
1.	Compact I	>4500	Darjeeling-Pulbazar, Gorubathan	70	26.02
2.	Semi-Compact (SC)	3000-4500	Rangli-Ranliot, Kalimpong –I, Kalimpong –II, Jorebunglow-Sukhiapokhri, Kurseong, Phansidewa	315	54.40
3.	Semi-Sprinkle (SP)	1500-3000	Mirik, Matigara, Naxalbari	158	13.45
4.	Dispersed (D)	0-1500	Kharibari	73	4.40

Source: Computed by Researcher

Compact Settlements: This type of rural settlement is characterized with agglomeration of almost all the dwellings of the mouza or village in one place (Ahmad, 1952). This is also known as nucleated or clustered settlement. Darjeeling -Pulbazar and Gorubathan CD Blocks fall under this type (index ranges above 4500). Darjeeling hills are clustered with settlements beyond Darjeeling town. The primacy of British preference, summer capital, and Tea and Tourism of Darjeeling town made the area a hub of employment. So, the villages of the area also densely populated. Gorubathan is a block of the district spread over both hills and plains. Having agriculture, tea, good transportation and recent development (after 1990s) of rural tourism made the area place of good employment. So the population and settlement are densely spread here.

Semi-Compact Settlements: The semi-compact settlements represents an intermediate type between compact and dispersed settlements. It is marked by the presence of one easily recognizable site (main cluster) and one or more small satellite settlements closely linked with the main site by roads. As the district under study is mostly a hilly terrain, the transport development of the district is also low. One of the biggest cause of forming Semi-compact settlement is under development in transport sector. Most of the CD Blocks of the district fall under this category (index ranges from 3000 to 4500). Rangli-Ranliot, Kalimpong –I, Kalimpong –II, Jorebunglow-Sukhiapokhri, Kurseong, Phansidewa are the Blocks having Semi-compact settlement.

Semi-Sprinkled Settlement: This type is characteristic feature of high water table areas, areas of numerous small streams with mountainous and forested areas of high relief where the facets of land is completely divided up (Mandal, 2001). Mirik, Matigara and Naxalbari blocks come under this type (index ranges from 1500 to 3000). The town bound development approach of planning made Mirik area under the shadow of Darjeeling and Kurseong town and similarly rural areas of Matigara and Naxalbari are under the shadow of Siliguri Municipal Corporation Area.

Dispersed Settlements: These settlements type cover very limited area, where scattered huts or homesteads found all over the village area and relatively long distance between dwellings. The dispersed type of rural settlements are found all over in the study region. Availability of water and arable land and means of transport are some of the factors responsible for the dispersal. The only of Darjeeling district falls under the type (index ranges 0 to 1500). Rural poverty, not being the place for aromatic Darjeeling tea and Darjeeling rural tourism trails and sharing national boundary with Kishanganj district, Bihar on the south and International boundary with Jhapa district of Nepal in the west made the area sparsely settled.

Two blocks need explanation over mathematical value. Block Phansidewa, located in tarai region and having facilities of plain area scored 4459 index value in 2011 census. It can be inevitably discussed that, this block will be under Compact settlement in the next Census. Block Jorebunglow-Sukhiapokhri scored just 3006 index value and can be said that with all characteristics of a hilly terrain it is almost a semi-sprinkled settlement. Newer approach of village tourism based on homestays, tea tourism and tourism route connecting Mirik to Ghoom and Darjeeling making the area densely settled.

Conclusion: In the overview of the analysis it can be seen that the impact of physiographic terrain is deeply noted. Other physical aspects affecting the types of rural settlement are positively correlated in the villages of the district. Other than these, most impacted economic factors are proximate location to Tea Garden and Tourist Spots. These factors also have positive correlation with types of rural settlements. The growth of rural settlement from 2001 to 2011 shows a steady state growth, that is, more CD blocks are likely to be densely settled. Studies of this kind will aid in effective regional planning, infrastructural development, agriculture management and historical analysis of land use and socio-cultural patterns.

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